

IMPLEMENTATION OF A COMPUTERIZED NUCLEAR CARDIOLOGY DATABASE ON THE VETERANS ADMINISTRATION FILEMAN SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The rapidly increasing volume of invasive and noninvasive cardiovascular procedures, complicated by inherent delays in the reporting and archiving of data, lead to the development of the FileMan based Nuclear Cardiology Database (NCD). FileMan is a hierarchical-relational database system written in standard MUMPS which has been implemented for a variety of uses at several Veterans Administration sites. It uses open architecture and is a public domain, vendor independent, fourth generation language capable of managing large data bases on personal computers, minicomputers and main frames. We report the first application of the FileMan to a comprehensive nuclear cardiology clinical database. The system is networked and maintains interactive databases capable of encompassing functions such as data entry, editing, formatting and printing of test results and procedure reports. It also provides for data searches, data display, tabulation, calculations and statistical analysis. System access, data entry, data definition, programming and security can be independently controlled. The NCD will be incorporated into the Cardiology Automation Program which has been implemented to manage

screen-oriented entry, editing and report generation for electrocardiograms, Holter monitoring studies, cardiac catheterization studies, electrophysiology studies, echocardiograms and exercise tolerance tests. The NCD provides multi-site access to vital data and even off-site, transtelephonic data retrieval.

INTRODUCTION

The VA FileMan Version 17.32 is a public domain database system written in standard MUMPS language which is currently in use at a number of Veterans Administration sites. We report on the implementation of the first Nuclear Cardiology Database using this system. The FileMan is a set of MUMPS "database" routines similar to a number of other MUMPS database systems written over the past 10 years.¹ The File Manager originated with database management system development efforts at Beth Israel Hospital in Boston in 1971.² George Timson has been credited with the essential design of the system. It is updated approximately twice a year.

The NCD utilizes a user friendly interactive dialogue with a terminal display that scrolls line by line. The use of terminal independent programs permits the FileMan system to run in virtually any computer environment that will

Figure 3. Tabulation of the number of studies performed on a quarterly basis (1983 to present).

through these tasks, the system interactively "prompts" or asks for input responses. The user types in a response, followed by a "return". On line "help" is available by typing "?" to get an explanation of allowable options. If the system does not accept the user's response to a prompt, it will sound an audible alarm, and repeat the question. The user is able to "back-up" to a previous question by use of a special "A" character.

Data Output: The main outputs from the FileMan system are output reports generated after dialog under the main menu options called PRINT FILE ENTRIES and INQUIRE TO FILE ENTRIES. In the former, the user enters "sort" specifications which will determine

which records appear in the output and determines the sequence of record output. When the sort sequence is sufficiently convoluted, the program will offer the user the opportunity to "save" the sort specifications in a template under a name the user specifies. This template can subsequently be recalled at will. A similar sequence is available for selection of fields to be printed out and selection of a report heading. FileMan will offer a default heading. The user will then be offered the opportunity to change the heading, enter a different heading, or elect not to have a report heading. Once the user has defined a list of more than five fields to be printed out, FileMan will offer the opportunity to save the list in a template. Print templates are similar to edit templates and once specified, can be invoked by name. Output device selection is an option which allows the user to print out or "send" the output report to virtually any word processing output device in the multi-site system.

Auxilliary functions include access and security. Security is maintained by a two tiered procedure for signing on whereby the user enter a 6 digit "access code" and a 6 digit "verification code". Access within the system is multi-tiered. "Read access" allows viewing of certain fields within the selected file. "Write access" allows viewing of data as well as data entry. A still higher level of security is "delete access", which entitles the user to erase and modify file entires. "Data definition access" is the highest level of

security generally reserved for the creator of the file and other delegated users.

REPORT GENERATION

The nuclear cardiology studies include acquisition and evaluation of complex patient data. Each study contains data which can be separated into six categories.

- 1) Demographic data
- 2) Anamnestic data
- 3) Patient history and reason for study
- 4) Measurements and calculations
- 5) Comments, complications, etc.
- 6) Impression and summary

There are principally three types of studies currently performed which are archived in the NCD;

1) Technecium 99-m Radionuclide Ventriculography (MUGA) studies. These include first pass studies, resting equilibrium studies and rest/exercise equilibrium studies.

2) Technicium 99-m pyrophosphate myocardial infarction (MI) studies.

3) Thallium-201 stress studies.

A typical report is shown in figure 2. Tabulation of the number of studies performed on a quarterly basis for the past five years is shown in figure 3. To date, 1300 studies on approximately 900 patients have been entered in the data base. Data may be accessed either by patient name, social security number or date of study. For teaching or research purposes, the database may be accessed, without knowledge of programming skills, by simply

entering into the system the Boolean "search criteria" on the basis of which the system can scan all or a portion of a file to generate a list of data entries that fulfill the specified conditions. The NCD currently runs on the Medical Center computer system which includes five Digital PDP 11/44 processors with 4 Mb memory, five 456 Mb fixed disks, and five 205 Mb removable disks for backup. System multiplexors link 450 I/O ports directly into the central unit.

FUTURE APPLICATIONS

Once the NCD has been thoroughly tested, it will be incorporated into the Cardiology Automation Program which has been implemented by the Veterans Administration for multi-site use.

CONCLUSIONS

A nuclear cardiology database has been implemented on the Veterans Administration FileMan system to facilitate storage and retrieval of cardiac scintigraphic studies. The database is interactive and allows twenty four hour access to data and printed reports of over 1300 studies.

REFERENCES

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